

MAKERERE

UNIVERSITY

COLLEGE OF HUMANITIES AND SOCIAL SCIENCES

SCHOOL OF WOMEN AND GENDER STUDIES

SOCIAL CAPITAL, GENDER AND THE SURVIVAL OF THE YOUTH IN KAMPALA: THE
CASE OF KATANGA SLUM

BY

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GLED (Mak)

A DISSERTATION SUBMITTED TO THE SCHOOL OF WOMEN AND GENDER STUDIES
IN PARTIAL FULFILLMENT FOR THE AWARD OF A POST-GRADUATE DIPLOMA IN
GENDER AND LOCAL ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF MAKERERE UNIVERSITY

NOVEMBER 2020

Declaration

This study is original and has not been submitted for any other degree award to any other University before.

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read "F. ...".

..... Signature of candidate

This thesis/dissertation has been submitted for examination with the approval of the following supervisor:

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Acknowledgment

This work is a result of various contributors. These include; my dear friend and Sister Ms. Faustine Nakazibwe.

My Supervisor, Dr. Evelyn Lutwama- Rukundo for all the guidance along the way.. May the Lord richly bless her!

My course coordinator Dr. May Sengendo, all that we learnt in LED is to a large extent reflected in this work – I'm very grateful!

The School Secretary Ms. Esther Namitala, you made my journey much easier for you were always available for any administrative issue. I'm very grateful!

My classmates in the Gender and Local Development course, you have all been wonderful to me and very supportive especially our class Monitor Agatha and Abel, you made my start much easier. Thank you so much! Not to forget Ambrose who always made learning fun and encouraged all of us in class. Thank you.

Lastly to the great **IAM** for without Him I can do nothing. All glory and honor goes back to Him. He is an awesome God!

Contents

Declaration	i
Acknowledgement	iii
List of Pictures	vi
List of Abbreviations	vii
Abstract	viii
CHAPTER ONE	1
1.0 Introduction	1
1.1 Statement of the Problem	5
1.2 Objectives	6
1.3 Significance of the Study	6
1.4 Scope of the Study	6
CHAPTER TWO	7
2.0 Literature Review	7
2.1 Gender and Social Capital	8
2.2 Elements of Social Capital leading to Local Economic Development	9
2.3 Participation as a Catalyst of Social Capital in Locality Development	11
2.4 Social capital and Economic survival	12
CHAPTER THREE	14
3.0 Methodology	14
3.1 Research methods and tools	14
3.2 Sample selection	14
3.3 Data management and analysis	15
3.4 Ethical considerations	15
3.5 Research limitations	15
CHAPTER FOUR	16
4.0 Presentation of findings	16
4.1 Findings	16
4.1.1 The kind of Social Capital utilized by young females for survival	16
4.2 Interpretation of results	21
4.3 The kind of Social Capital utilized by young males for survival	22
4.4 Interpretation of results	31
4.4.2 Partners involved	32

4.4.3	Gendered use of social capital.....	32
4.4	Discussion of Findings from a Local Economic Development Perspective.....	33
4.5	Conclusion.....	34
CHAPTER FIVE.....		35
5.0	Introduction.....	35
5.1	Summary on Findings.....	35
5.2	Recommendations.....	35
5.3	Conclusion.....	36

List of Pictures

Picture 1. An over view of Katanga slum with a garage nearby.....	23
Picture 2 - One of the food vendors in Katanga Slum	28
Picture 3 - One of the scrap centers in Katanga.....	30
Picture 4 - At the extreme right is the shelter where some sleep at night	31

List of Abbreviations

ILO - International Labour Organisation

IOM - International Organization for Migration

LED - Local Economic Development

SACCO -Savings and Credit Cooperative Society

UNICEF - United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund

UN - United Nations

UNAIDS - United Nations Programme on HIV/AIDS

UYN - Uganda Youth Network

Abstract

This study sought to explore how young women and men in slums survived through the use of social capital. The study specifically focused on establishing the kind of social capital used and the gendered use of social capital among young females and males and partners involved in the survival of young people. The study was qualitative in nature. Unstructured interviews, non-participant observation and document analysis methods were used to collect data. This research was conducted in Katanga slum situated in Kampala district.

The results show that all three major forms of social capital were used by young women and men in Katanga slum for survival. The *bonding*, *linking* and *bridging* forms of social capital were utilized to have income generating activities. Linking social capital, however, was to a large extent missing among young women, due to a number of reasons including, lack of collateral security, limited time due to triple roles, poor information flow on economic issues among women which greatly affects their wellbeing and consequently local economic development. Therefore bottle necks to women's full participation in local development initiatives should be addressed by local authorities like local councils, government and Non-governmental organizations.

The study is therefore relevant to social workers especially those working in slum areas and local councils in promoting social capital building as a catalyst to job creation and resource, availability.

CHAPTER ONE

1.0 Introduction

Globally, over 1 billion people live in slums and this represents a quarter of the world's population (Friesen et al., 2019; Habitat for Humanity Britain, 2017). Some of the World's largest slums include Dharavi in Mumbai – India, Orange town in Karachi – Pakistan, (Habitat for Humanity Britain, 2017) ; Manshiyat Nasser in Cairo – Egypt, Port au Prince- Haiti, Tondo in Manila- Phillipines (Overdorf, 2019).

With increased rapid urbanization, it is estimated that by 2030, 2 billion people will be living in slums (Habitat for Humanity Ireland, 2018). Africa also hosts some of the world's largest slums for instance Kibera and Mathare in Nairobi – Kenya, Kyayelitsha in Cape town – South Africa (Habitat for Humanity, 2016); Ajegunle and Shomolu in Lagos – Nigeria, Cazenga in Luanda- Angola, Agbogblshie in the southern part of Ghana (Mutuku, 2020). In Uganda, some of Kampala's slums include Bwaise, Kabalagala, Katwe, Kisenyi,(IOM, 2017) Katanga, Kikoni among others.

The majority of slum dwellers in developing countries are aged between 15 to 25 years as cited in the Policy Brief of Uganda Youth Network (2015) and this is the age bracket that constitutes the youth according to the National Youth Council Act (Government of Uganda, 1998). For the case of Uganda about 65% of the slum dwellers are youth. Uganda is the second youngest country in Africa with a median age of 16 years (Maniraj, 2017). This young population is a result of the high death rates among adults and increase in orphaned children due to mainly the HIV/AIDS scourge in Uganda which was at its peak in the 1990s. At that time, 30% of pregnant women and 18 % of the general population infected according to Stoneburner and Low-Beer (as cited in Yebra et al., 2015) . The death rates were over 75,000 per year in the late 1980s and early 1990s (Relief Web, 2016) Today over 1.3 million adults are living with HIV, and annually over 23,000 people in Uganda die of AIDS related illnesses annually (UNAIDS, 2020). War has also displaced 2.3 million people after 2 decades of conflict in Northern Uganda of which 12.4% were children by then (WHO, 2006) and the 1986 coup where many people were left homeless and others orphaned (Peace Direct, 2017) . Some of these displaced persons ended up in slums thus creating a big vulnerable youth group which is approximately 65% according to the Ministry of Gender Labour and Social Development (as cited in UYONET, 2015).

About 64% of the urban population are youth and living in slums according to the Ministry of Lands Housing and Urban Development (2015). Youth Unemployment is at 83% (World Bank, 2008) and the Ugandan Economy can only absorb 20% of its youth (UYN, 2015). Others are under employed in the informal sector, with poor working conditions, very low pay since they are not skilled and as such end up just surviving without actually progressing in their living conditions or realizing their full potential in as far as their economic wellbeing is concerned (PSUP, 2016).

Living in slums is tough, with poor basic infrastructure like healthcare and sanitation services, poor education facilities, high unemployment among other problems experienced. Many youth resort to activities like vending food and drinks in the business areas in order to survive. However some relatively progressive youth are employed as mobile money business operators among other businesses. They do not own the mobile money business but are able to earn between 27 to 54 USD per month as operators of the businesses (FSD Uganda & FRIENDS Consult, 2017). Other slum dwellers engage in street begging, making and selling local brew and chapati. Social behaviors such as the use of drugs and prostitution are common in the area (IOM, 2018 : p.49). Poverty, insecurity high crime rates, sexual abuse are part of Kampala slums(Kids Club Kampala, 2016). The above characteristics are associated with low social capital (Kay, 2006; Woolcock, 1998).

Katanga slum is no different from the above picture, it is within Kampala and part of the 56 informal settlements in Kampala city which accommodates 1.6 million people, of which 70% live in slums according to UNICEF (as cited in Kids Club Kampala, 2016). Katanga slum covers about 50.6 acres of land from Wandegeya to Kubiri located in the valley between Makerere University and Mulago Hospital. It is home to over five thousand people with over one thousand households (Act Together & National Slum Dwellers Federation, 2014).

As discussed above, slum dwellers suffer from many social, economic and environmental challenges which can be addressed through various dimensions and this study looks at the social capital dimension in addressing the youth slum dwellers economic survival. Social capital is an asset that can enhance forms of capital for better livelihoods and local economic development.

Social capital is about relationships that allow humans to collaborate, coordinate and coexist (Tristan Claridge, 2004). It is therefore essential to human social existence. Social capital refers to features of social organization such as networks, norms and social trust that facilitate coordination and cooperation for mutual benefit (Putnam, 1995: p.67). It can also be referred to as

the value of the relationships between people who work or live together and the knowledge and skills that they have and share(*Cambridge English Dictionary*, 2019). According to Amartya Sen (2001), Social capital is understood as trust, norms and networks that enable collective action, for instance, in entrepreneurship and economic development. Social capital are social relations which facilitate economic exchanges(Trigilia, 2001). The above definitions clearly indicate that the mechanism that drives social capital has to do with transmitting information, establishing trust and promoting norms of collaboration (Hassan & Birungi, 2011).

The economic benefit of social capital (networks, relationships) is seen through the facilitation of knowledge transmission about the behavior of others, and these repetitive transactions establish trust and reputations, facilitate transmission of knowledge about technology and markets thus reduce market failures due to information exchange. Social capital's reliance on norms and rules reduces exploitation thus promoting cooperative action according to Collier (as cited in Hassan & Birungi, 2011).

Local development and social capital go hand in hand and they tend to reinforce each other according to Putnam (as cited in Australian Bureau of Statistics, 2002). There is a direct relationship between the volume of social capital and economic development since economic development is more likely to occur in social systems with strong social networks and trust as highlighted by Coleman (Midgley & Livermore, 1998 p:31).

Therefore, Slums are not economically developed because of the existence of low social capital. Low social capital is described as any situation where there is lack of social structure and organization and where people are prone to act antisocially(Tristan Claridge, 2014). This limitation is in addition to low levels of education, patronage and contacts as well as a general exclusion of slum dwellers from 'regular society'. These conditions result in constraints on empowerment and access to sources of finance to develop slum dwellers' own livelihoods (United Nations Human Settlements Programme, 2003 : p6). On the other hand, people who are rich in social capital have more social resources which they can call upon when searching for a job, relations developed through the education system, one's educational level and social support or political power(Tirmizi, 2005 : 31).Areas with high social capital attract investments and therefore more businesses and employment opportunities leading to locality development (United Nations Human Settlements Programme, 2003). For example, according to the Global Sustainable

Competitiveness Index (2017), the top 10 leading countries in social capital are Norway, Luxembourg, Iceland, Finland, Germany, Switzerland, Japan, South Korea, Slovenia and Netherlands while Sweden takes on the 11th position out of 180 countries surveyed. These countries are highly developed. The 10 least ranking countries in social capital from the bottom are Central African Republic, Democratic Republic of Congo, Kiribati, Swaziland, Fiji, Guyana, Gambia, Lesotho, Yemen, and Haiti. These are least developed countries.

Social capital can be broken down into bridging, linking and bonding social capital (Australian Bureau of Statistics, 2002; Mpanje, Gibbons, & McDermott, 2018). Bridging Social capital refers to relationships across groups regardless of power relations (Schneider, 2004) or relations that stretch beyond a shared sense of identity like distant colleagues or distant friends whose outcomes can be economic, political or social(Mpanje et al., 2018).

Linking social capital refers to vertical ties between the poor and people in positions of influence in formal organizations like banks, agricultural extension offices, and police among others (World Bank, 2001:p.128).

Bonding Social capital refers to personal relations that are based on a sense of collective identity such as family, ethnicity, close friendship or sharing the same culture and these relations influence mental, health, life satisfaction and economic wellbeing (Mpanje et al., 2018, p. 3).

According to Putnam (1995) it is the linking and bridging types of social capital that break through boundaries of status, power and are crucial to economic development. High levels of bridging social capital represent high levels of trust, crucial to economic activities like savings and investments in addition to civic participation (Legatum Institute, 2018).For example an example of trust is seen when a neighbor borrows some sugar to make pancakes for her children instead of driving to a town which is 15km away. This saves time and money in terms of transport or fuel and at the same time builds norms of reciprocity that can benefit both parties in the future. Another example is when one passes on a skill to another person like weaving mats, growing flowers or mechanical work. These skills can be put to use and one is able to earn and make a living(Tristan Claridge, 2014).

Therefore with limited financial and human capital in slums, exploring ways of benefitting more from these limited resources through social capital could be helpful in accessing skills and

financial capital thus improving the livelihood of slum dwellers (Evans & Syrett, 2007). Social capital in this case is a means to accessing what one does not have through the relational networks in form of linking social capital/ social relations with those in authority or power) and bridging social capital/relationships across groups regardless of power relations). Through linking up with those in power and authority, the young men and women can have access to education, skilling opportunities and credit facilities where they can start up their own small businesses and earn a decent living. Therefore, the role of social capital in promoting building of small enterprises (a LED pillar) is explored in the survival of youth in slums or in improving their wellbeing.

It is also worth noting that social capital can be an asset or liability, it has benefits and costs as well (Trigilia, 2001). Social capital is beneficial and an asset when one gets positive outcomes and a liability when one makes losses. For instance, in a slum area, it can be costly when young people get involved in criminal activities instead of local developmental activities. However, in this study we shall look at the positive or economic role of social capital in improving the livelihood of slum dwellers.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

Slums are areas with low economic development characterized by poor infrastructure, high crime rate among others (Kay, 2006). People in these areas do not have adequate connections, linkages or networks to those in power and authority who can assist them make their lives better through access to jobs and better infrastructure like housing and sanitation which would improve their wellbeing. Both Bridging and linking social capital are low within slums (Woolcock, 1998; Woolcock et al. 2000) and yet these are key to accessing those in power and authority, who are have influence and control of economic resources.

In a survey carried out in the slums of Kampala, only 44.3% of the youth are employed. These are mainly engaged in petty businesses where they are self-employed, or work as casual laborers at construction sites. Others deal in street vending, “boda-boda” riding, drug dealing, prostitution among others (IOM, 2017 : p.14). As such, young women and men can hardly earn enough to take care of their basic needs.

Therefore, with limited education, resources, what forms of social capital are at the youth’s disposal in Katanga and how can they utilize these forms of social capital to improve their

wellbeing? In addition to the above, limited literature is available on the role of social capital in uplifting the wellbeing of young women and men in slums hence the need to carry out this research.

1.2 Objectives

The purpose of this study is to investigate how the different forms of social capital can be put to use in slum areas to improve the wellbeing of young women and men. That is;

- a) Establish the kind of social capital which young females and males in Katanga utilize for survival.
- b) Explore the gendered use of social capital by young females and males in Katanga.
- c) Investigate the partners involved in facilitating the survival of young people in Katanga.

1.3 Significance of the Study

This study is relevant to local development workers for they are able to consciously use locally available resources including social capital as one of the resources. For instance linking social capital institutions like micro finance institutions, local governments are consciously utilized so that their activities are aligned to local government plans. Social workers are able to maximize and build social capital among various, persons and communities through community activities. Community institutions like churches, mosques, can be used as avenues of building and utilizing social capital among their members for local community development initiatives.

Local councils and Kampala City Authority can plan for slums while consciously promoting positive social capital building as a resource and as a way of enhancing local economic development. Positive social capital enhances creativity and innovation thus promoting the creation of jobs for slum dwellers and bringing about local economic development.

1.4 Scope of the Study

The study focuses on young men and women of Katanga slum and how they use social capital particularly in informal work in order to earn a living.

CHAPTER TWO

2.0 Literature Review

The term social capital came onto the scene two decades ago fronted by sociologists like Putnam (1993 and 2000) and later found its way to the Economic and Employment Policy of the European Union coined up as Local Social Capital. Later the World Bank through its famous CONSCISE report of 2001-2003 which sought to find out how social capital could be measured, produced and reproduced. Social capital is about a collective set of resources built on inter-human relationships (Birkhölzer, 2009).

Social capital is intangible though its effects are visible with a deeper analysis of the social environment which could be friendly (Kay, 2006). This creates room for creativity and innovations thus contributing to local development.

According to the Legatum Prosperity Index (2020), where a unique insight into how prosperity is forming and changing across the world through the use of different variables including social capital, Uganda was ranked 124th in social capital out of 167 countries globally and Uganda's economic living conditions were ranked at 142. Kenya was ranked at 49th position in social capital and 133 in the economic wellbeing of its people while Burundi was at 148th position in social capital and 164 in economic wellbeing. This clearly shows that social capital contributes to the economic wellbeing of a country. Countries ranking high in social capital tend to do better in as far as economic development is concerned.

Denmark, the leading country in social capital was also number one in the economic wellbeing of its people, Norway 2nd in social capital and 8th in economic wellbeing while Finland is in the 3rd position of social capital and 9th in economic wellbeing of its people. South Sudan was ranked 165th position in social capital and 166th position in economic wellbeing while Central African Republic was in the 161st position in social capital and 167th position in economic wellbeing (Legatum Institute, 2020). This clearly shows that to some extent, social capital contributes to the wellbeing of people, for countries with better social capital rankings are also doing well economically.

It is worth highlighting the fact that promoting social capital development in slums is needed for inclusive local development. When the youth are not taken care of in terms of jobs and innovation opportunities, their economic potential is lost. When other areas of the city are under developed, and the poor or vulnerable ignored, cities become unsafe and those who live therein live in fear and consequently it becomes very costly to manage such cities. When those with money and expertise leave the city centers because of violence, such cities will never maximize their potential in local economic development (Rowntree, 2016). Therefore building social capital especially *linking social capital*, which involves individuals and institutions is key in attracting other forms of capital like finance and human capital, investments, job opportunities among other benefits. Consequently, residents improve their wellbeing, especially the youth, for they are able to meet their basic needs, thus bringing about locality development. According to Rowntree (2016), social capital is not an extra option in local development but it is as fundamental as financial and human capital for inclusive local economic development.

2.1 Gender and Social Capital

Access to social capital greatly differs among women and men. Men tend to be more in networks with political and economic advantages such as business opportunities while women are more in non-monetary labor exchanges within the domestic environment (Molyneux, 2002). A study by Norris & Inglehart (2003) further confirms this, for it highlights women as more involved in education, arts, voluntary organizations, church activities and women organizations while men are more active in political parties, sports clubs, professional associations and unions plus community associations. The contribution of volunteer or unpaid work, where women are concentrated, is often not taken into account much as it plays a significant role in local economic development. For instance, according to the National Federation of Sports in Germany, 2.6 million volunteers estimated to be an equivalent of 4.5 billion euros in wages, of which 24% of these were women and youth in Germany (Birkhölzer, 2009). The contribution of unpaid/volunteer work in this case is much more in the African context. In addition, time, poverty and mobility restrictions due to the triple roles shouldered by women greatly limits the women's mobility and economic networks and opportunities when compared to men. It is important to note that maintaining social networks is costly in terms of finances, for one needs to move especially if they are to utilize the *bridging* and *linking* forms of social capital.

The micro credit facilities which often feature in the *linking social capital* that have been availed to poor women are gender blind in a way that it is men who control these micro-credit facilities (Molyneux, 2002). In most cases men are not in position to understand the challenges that women go through to meet collateral needs or pay back in time. As such, men benefit much more for they are able to work and earn more without much hindrances like mobility restrictions due to triple role limitations. Consequently men are able to refund the money back to micro credit institutions in good time since they also have collateral security thus taking care of their basic needs better and improving their livelihood. Women have tried to create groups so as to access credit from micro finance institutions but the credit extended to them is so little and as such, they engage in petty businesses where they do not earn much.

2.2 Elements of Social Capital leading to Local Economic Development

Evans (2007) describes social capital elements as resources within communities which are created through the presence of high levels of trust, reciprocity and mutuality, shared norms of behavior, shared commitment and belonging, both formal and informal social networks and effective communication channels. Absence of social capital or low levels of social capital are evident in neighborhoods with few social networks, lack of trust, norms and no commitment to the area leading to social under development. This is further evidenced by increase in crime, mutual suspicion, lack of information, few social facilities, poor health facilities, a degraded physical environment in general (Kay, 2006 : p.167).

Trust is key in the maintenance of social capital and it needs time to develop and grow over a number of social interactions (Kay, 2006). Trust is at the same time fragile for it takes time to develop but can be destroyed in just a moment for with mistrust, cooperation between individuals, organizations is hampered, and economic opportunities for mutual development lost thus affecting local development (Kay, 2006).

Norms are mental models that structure our beliefs about actions that others are likely to take in specific contexts, actions that others should take in those contexts, and the degrees to which we personally uphold and we expect others to uphold these standards of behavior (Weaver, 2018, p. 19). For instance, in Uganda especially in the central region, people used to do certain activities collectively for the good of society. For instance, repairing roads, digging wells, cleaning markets

or the environment and all these benefited society and contributed to the wellbeing of all. Failure to be a part of these activities was and is still seen as being anti-social and can lead to exclusion within the community.

Strong reciprocity is another social capital element which is also a norm that includes cooperating with others for the good of a larger social group, the willingness to punish those who do not cooperate and defending the group against anti-social actions that affect their wellbeing(Weaver, 2018, p. 23). Reciprocity further encourages the individual to balance their own self-interest for the good of the community, therefore individuals can for instance, provide part of their land to have a bore hole, or a road for the wellbeing of the community(Australian Bureau of Statistics, 2002).

Networking is another avenue through which social networks are built. For instance in groups that have similar affiliations like religion, ethnicity or geographical specifications create bonding social capital. Coordinated behavior is expected and where community members evaluate one another against tacit or explicit local norms to the extent that individuals who identify with a particular place tend to adhere to the conventions of that particular place (Weaver, 2018, p. 25).

Social networks therefore enable the circulation of information and trust leading to economic consequences for development. Social networks lower the cost of transaction in the market place (Evans & Syrett, 2007; Trigilia, 2001). For instance, when one knows where the best price for their produce or labor is, they save on time and resources and consequently earn better as well. The above attributes therefore influence the formation of entrepreneurial activities thus facilitating development in a particular area (Trigilia, 2001:p. 428-429).

According to Roberts(1985), the basic principle of local development is about generating “local work for local people using local resources”(as cited in Birkhölzer, 2009). Local economic development is a special economic self-help strategy originally invented for disadvantaged groups or communities at a local or regional level(Birkhölzer, 2009:p.5).

It is important to highlight the fact that social capital is an asset that exists among individuals and organizations within a community. It is different from other forms of capital for it does not wear out, the more it is used, the more it generates more social capital for more relationships are created (Kay, 2006) which can be utilized for generation of tacit knowledge and development of human

capital plus other advantages. It is a public good enjoyed by all members of a group and by-product of other activities(Švihlová & Kubišová, 2014).

It is also important to note that social capital is not a substitute for other forms of capital but should be used in addition to other forms of capital like, physical, financial and human capital (Kay, 2006; Švihlová & Kubišová, 2014).

2.3 Participation as a Catalyst of Social Capital in Locality Development

Participation is a local development principle and an element of social capital, in that the beneficiaries of social capital are mainly those who actively participate or network with others. This is well articulated in the Local Economic Development definition (LED) below;

*LED is a locally-owned, **participatory** development process undertaken within a given territory or local administrative area in partnership with both public and private stakeholders. The LED approach makes use of local resources and competitive advantages to create decent employment and sustainable economic growth (Musvoto, Nortje, Nahman, & Stafford, 2018 : p.105).*

Participation creates networks, relationships through which persons can benefit from each other in terms of information access, skills, financial capital and other locally available resources and this is what local economic development is all about. Therefore high levels of *linking social capital*(ability to associate with funding or skilling institutions) and *bridging social capital* (being open to those who are better than you in status, knowledge, et cetera) are key in boosting the LED process thus creating private and public partnerships for enterprise development and employment opportunities. It is important to highlight the fact that social networking facilitates social capital building. Therefore access to social capital is restricted to those who participate in social networks (Evans & Syrett, 2007).

Local economic development is practiced in various parts of the world today. It is based on practical experience, improved by trial and error thus learning from successes and failures of others (Birkhölzer, 2009). Therefore networking (building social capital) becomes key in developing local economic strategies. A social audit in eight localities across 5 European countries namely England (London-Waltham Forest); Scotland(Benarty); German(Kreuzberg and Wedding); Sweden(Umea and Nastansjo); Spain(Bercelona and La Mina) revealed that social enterprises

build and use social capital. The two phases (building and using) could not be distinguished since using social capital is actually building it as well. That is, the more it is used, the more it grows (Evans & Syrett, 2007). The above discussion clearly shows that for local economic development to take place, individualism has no place and unity has always been power.

2.4 Social capital and Economic survival

The World Bank promotes economic growth through utilization of social capital formation as a poverty reduction strategy. Non-Governmental Organizations are welcoming this strategy too (Muthusamy, 2011). Today tangible results of social capital are seen in different parts of the world. India for instance, has reduced the impact of poverty through the utilization of social capital on the welfare of the poor through income generation are evident. In this regard, social capital has facilitated management of common resources, access to credit and education services and effective flow of information relevant to the poor through micro and macro channels (Muthusamy, 2011). In fact, thousands of the poor and marginalized population in India are now re-building their lives through self-help groups (which promote networking, social capital building and collateral security). The self-help groups have attracted the attention of Government, Non-governmental organizations and consequently, people have gained easy access to micro loans through micro finance institutions at very low interest rates for their micro enterprises (Sundaram, 2012).

Self-help groups are informal associations of people who choose to come together and seek ways of improving their living conditions (Khasnabis et al., 2010). These are groups of about 15 to 20 members. Through group savings, credit and social involvement or networking, using agreed upon rules and norms, they are able to save regularly as a group and rotate credit among themselves (Muthusamy, 2011).

Consequently, Kampala slum dwellers have come up with saving and credit services such as rotating credit services and saving groups based on social ties and social capital. The purpose of these credit services and saving groups is to lend money as a revolving fund mechanism, mainly to boost small scale businesses, build houses, pay school fees, and meet other basic needs (Avuni, 2011: p. 38) thus improving on the wellbeing of the slum dwellers.

Self- help groups have played a big role in poverty alleviation, though increase in employment opportunities and income generating activities plus raising the status of women and men in society (Sundaram, 2012).

In South Africa, Self-help groups have been embraced in South Africa to cater for part of the 40% unemployed youth and consequently the lives of these youth has tremendously improved. The youth are able to save, invest in crop production, poultry, farming, participate in computer skills training among other income generating activities(Global giving, 2019). Kenya has also done the same and is even going a step further in easing communication among the different self-help groups through mobile solutions(Masita-Mwangi, Ronoh-Boreh, & Aruwa, 2011). Self-help groups in Kenya promote economic empowerment of members through savings, access to loans , asset acquisition and trainings (Atieno, 2017). It is also important to note that self-help groups are limited in finances but the strong bonds that are created also have other social benefits where members tend to care for one another(Nyataya, 2016).

In Uganda, self-help groups have also been encouraged among the poor especially in slums. For example Kinawataka Women's Initiative got support from the United States of American Embassy in the form of *linking social capital*. The beneficiaries were able to meet a weaved mats order for an International School in Uganda. This Women's initiative also makes jewelry, bags and other fashion accessories that are sold in different souvenir stores in Uganda (US Embassy, 2011). A similar self-help group - Child Restoration Outreach operating in Mbale, Jinja, Lira and Masaka districts encourages its members to save and invest in microbusinesses where they earn interest on their savings. It is envisaged that the savings could be used to take care of their beneficiaries financial needs such as education and business investments (Child Restoration Outreach, 2019). It herefore strongly believe that social capital development through self-help groups will go along well in improving the welfare of young slum dwellers in Kampala.

CHAPTER THREE

3.0 Methodology

The study takes on a qualitative approach for social capital is qualitative in nature to a large extent. This calls for an in-depth understanding of the subject with detailed descriptions. Qualitative methods allow use of a small sample of participants with an in-depth study thus providing detailed information (Open university, 2019). The researcher also had limited time so the qualitative approach was appropriate for the study.

3.1 Research methods and tools

Qualitative research methods have been used. These include in-depth interviews, and observation. The in-depth interviews allow face to face interaction, ability to clarify or question further on any response and do observation as well. Participants emotions, feelings, opinions are observed during the face to face interviews and the required data was recorded (Langos, 2014). In cases of discomfort on the part of the respondent, emotional support was offered thus remaining on course and collecting the required data (McIntosh & Morse, 2015).

Non participant observation was used and here the researcher watched, recorded, and interpreted what had been observed (Pickard, 2007). Observation is also a confirmatory method that to some extent verified information from other data collection sources. Consequently, an overview of the survival of young people was captured through sight in a short period of time. In this case, the data collection took two days.

Documentary Analysis has been used to get more information on Katanga slum. That is from reports and other research papers that have been written on Katanga. Consequently, a deeper understanding on the survival of youth in relation to social capital utilization is attained.

3.2 Sample selection

Purposive sampling was used. Information rich cases were identified basing on particular cases that are rich in information and relevant to the research project (Pickard, 2007). Since it was a qualitative research and the researcher had limited time, 5 females and 6 males in the youth category (18-35 years old) were identified basing on the major income generating activities within Katanga slum.

Income generating activity (men - 1 boda boda rider, 1 mechanic from the garages in Katanga, 1 chapati/ chips vendor, 1 car washer, 1 mobile money agent and 1 scrap dealer who is also a resident of Katanga slum). Income generating activity (women – 1 pool table attendant, 1 cook from the small hotels of Katanga, 1 mobile money agent, 1 tailor, and 1 hair dresser who is also a resident of Katanga).

3.3 Data management and analysis

The interviews were recorded and documented at the same time to ensure that relevant information was captured. Then themes and categories were generated as data was analyzed from the stories of various respondents in respect to the objectives of the study. The data analysis was done with a gender perspective. The names of the respondents are not revealed to ensure confidentiality.

3.4 Ethical considerations

Participants did respond to the interview at their own free will and their identities are not revealed. Participants were not abused in any way whether physically or psychologically but rather a conducive environment of comfort was created during the interviews.

3.5 Research limitations

There was limited time for the research. The 11 participants selected for the sample size might not be representative enough of Katanga slum as far as a representative sample size is concerned but, they do give an over view picture of economic survival of youth in Katanga slum.

CHAPTER FOUR

4.0 Presentation of findings

The findings of this study are qualitative in nature and presented in a narrative format to establish the kind of social capital young people in Katanga utilize for their survival. The gendered use of social capital among these young people. The partners (linking social capital) involved in facilitating the survival of young women and men in Katanga. The participants were aged between 18 to 35 years old. These comprised of 5 women and 6 men. Pseudo-names are used in these narratives as a means of concealing the real identity of the participants.

4.1 Findings

Findings indicate that Bonding and Bridging social capital greatly contribute to the survival of young women and men as narrated below.

4.1.1 The kind of Social Capital utilized by young females for survival

Anita, 33 years old is a hair dresser. She has a small saloon in Katanga that sells a few other hair products. I find her plaiting one of the university students. Anita is a single mother. This is her story.

I first worked for another person, collected some capital and started my own saloon. I have a friend that I met at PRIDE Microfinance who gave me a small loan since she is a money lender. This private arrangement was good for me, for PRIDE Microfinance asks for collateral security like a land title, motor vehicle registration card or motor cycle card and several other requirements which I do not have. I do make payments on the loan on a monthly basis. I have been paying off my last loan for the last 5 months. The rules are followed when servicing the loan which at times is a challenge for I might not earn enough to service the loan. However, I have to service the loan on the agreed upon date without fail. In spite of this challenge, I have gained from the money lending service much as I do not enjoy any other social benefit from the relationship with the money lender. It is purely business.

From the above, it is clear that the kind of social capital utilized by Anita is the *bridging* social capital which allows benefiting from distant relationships.

Anita's response on partners

I have no idea of any NGO support in our area yet would have loved these NGOs to consider women especially and avail us with some capital for our businesses.

Anita and gendered use of social capital

From my perspective men are the most beneficiaries of PRIDE microfinance for they can at least meet collateral security requirements which most women do not have like land titles or motor cycle registration cards. However our survival needs are the same both in business and at home. I have personally not benefited from any institution apart from the loans I get from the money lender. Government has also not supported us in any way and I do not know why this is so. However, I do hear about a skills training school in the neighborhood skilling young people in hairdressing and tailoring. However, they seem to prefer those in their 20s so I cannot benefit from such a program.

4.1.2 Barbara

She is a 35 year old married tailor in Katanga. She does her tailoring on the balcony of one of the small shops.

I got tailoring training for one year through my parents and later started this business through my personal savings and money from "Kameeza" (this is money normally left at home by the husband to meet daily needs in the home). So my business exits today because of my parents plus my husband and my major principle for my business has been saving. My husband has been very helpful in my social life too.

Barbra uses the *bonding* social capital. This involves personal relations that are based on a sense of collective identity such as family, ethnicity or close friendship.

Barbra's response on partners

I have not benefited from any government intervention so I cannot comment on how men and women benefit from such. I also do not know why government has not intervened in our lives or NGOs. However, if an opportunity comes up, I would gladly embrace it. It is important to highlight the fact that in many cases, leaders who are sent to assist us at the grass root level never reach us

Barbra and gendered use of social capital

I have not benefited from any institution and I do not know how men survive. Microfinance institutions always want their money returned in time together with profits and I do not want that pressure. Here in Katanga on a good day, I can earn 50,000/- (fifty thousand shillings) which I cannot earn in Gayaza where I reside. These days business is low so I can earn about 20,000 to 30,000/- thirty thousand shillings daily on average.

The survival needs of men and women are not different so we cost share. For instance my husband pays school fees for the children and I buy uniforms and contribute to the “Kameeza” as well. In my case, I came with two children in my current marriage so I pay school fees for these children.

As far as networks are concerned, men are more active in networks as compared to women. For financial networks, women have a challenge of returning the money, much as they are involved in some income generating activities. These institutions always want their money no matter the returns one is making. However, if these institutions can give us ample time to return this money, I would also want to benefit from their services.

It is interesting to note that Katanga slum attracts people who reside distances away but come to work in this place. Barbra travels about 12 miles from Gayaza to work in Katanga which is more rewarding than working in Gayaza. Therefore, these slums can support the livelihood of the slum dwellers if well supported by government and civil society organizations. This is further highlighted by Overdorf (2019) where slums are seen with the potential of being hives of industry and ambition.

4.1.3 Carol

Carol is 18 years old. She deals in mobile money and sells a few electrical accessories in a tiny shop. She is still a single young lady.

I'm running my sister's business and everything here is owned by my sister. I have worked here for the last 6 months. We have no particular rules/principles for our business. For the rest of my other needs and social life, my mother and my sister take care of them.

From the above, it is clear that Carol is involved in *bonding* social capital.

Carol's response on partners

I have not heard of any institutions that can support me but would definitely want to be a part of these networks. I have not experienced any government or NGO support in our area and I do not know why. However, I would want to benefit from such networks if the opportunity comes up.

Carol and gendered use of social capital

I think the survival needs of men and women are the same for my mother provides for my brother and me in the same way.

4.1.4 Dorah

Dorah is a pool table operator. She is 25 years old and a single young lady.

I just came to town looking for work and came across a lady who also wanted someone to manage a pool table for her. I had never done this kind of work before but she taught me and supported me for 3 months and today I can manage by myself. I have no specific rules on this job, I work and manage my time as I wish.

Therefore the kind of social capital utilized by Dorah is the *bridging* social capital as highlighted in the above narrative.

Dorah's response on partners

I have not been able to benefit from government or any Nongovernmental organization. I also do not know why government has not come down to support us. However, if an opportunity comes up, I would be interested in participating in government or NGO developmental activities like skills training especially hair dressing or catering.

Dorah and gendered use of social capital

The only support in this business is from my boss and I do not have support from other persons or institutions. However, our survival needs differ a bit from the survival needs of men. We as women just need money for our personal needs while men need more money to take care of their girlfriends. For the little time I have spent here, I have not been able to interact with any institution or have strong networks with other people for trust takes time to build. I would love to be a part of other networks but this requires money.

4.1.5 Enid

She sells cooked food, porridge, tea and other drinks to the people in Katanga. The cooking shelter is within a car garage compound. She is 19 years old and a single young lady.

I came to town looking for a job since I could not continue with school any more. I came across Maama Namazi (my employer) who gave me this job and I have so far worked for one year. We are not related in any way. Maama Namazi has taught me how to be polite to customers and serve food and drinks in good time. My boss and I have business principles that have helped us grow and maintain this business. In fact am able to run the business even when Maama Namazzi is absent. Through this food business am able to meet my basic needs and I hope to start my own food business in future. We also help each other at times of need, for instance when one has a sick patient or lost a loved one.

The kind of social capital utilized by Enid therefore is *bridging* (benefiting from distant relationships) as highlighted in the narration above.

Enid's response on partners

I have not benefited from any government intervention or NGO initiative yet if they are made available both men and women can benefit. However the greatest challenge is that leaders of various groups including government officials take the resources that are allocated to the groups and the government policies oppress us and our businesses. For example, the use of tear gas to suppress Makerere student riots disrupts our food business. This makes us abandon our food since potential customers run away too and we therefore make huge losses. Government should purpose to make user friendly policies and endeavor to have its resources reach us.

Enid and gendered use of social capital

Well, in this garage we have a SACCO but it is only for men. I never see women participating yet we would like to benefit from such too to improve our businesses and take care of our families. With food business, at times the customer does not pay on that very day and you have to be patient for some days since you know them yet the suppliers of food need their money, so this becomes a big challenge in business yet we are not in SACCOs or financial networks. In addition to the above some of these SACCOs are closed to friends and not open to other people especially SACCOS run by women.

Our survival needs may differ depending on some one's personality. Some men love fun and vice versa while in my case I would love to have income generating projects like rental houses and have some money for shopping as well.

From Enid's submission, survival needs have nothing to do with gender but rather personalities or individual differences.

4.2 Interpretation of results

Forms of Social capital and utilization by young women

Therefore from the above, it is clear that young women utilize more of the bonding and bridging social capital for their survival while the linking social capital is greatly missing. From the above narrations, none of the five young women is utilizing linking social capital. This conforms to earlier scholar observations, Norris and Inglehart (2003), which indicated that women are seen more in voluntary networks or non-economic networks. These by nature fall within the bonding and bridging forms of social capital. The lack of linking social capital (social relations with those in authority or power) among women is attributed to financial limitations and limited access to information about such networks as highlighted in the narrations above.

Partner's involved in the survival of young women

No linking social capital (government or civil society organizations) is seen or productive local partnerships for women as indicated above for local economic development. The young women are interested in government/ civil society support as a partnership but they have no access to such initiatives yet these are institutions that have resources and power to change certain things in their society and promote local economic development. This is attributed to that fact young women have limited information to access economic networks or linking social capital initiatives and they lack collateral security too.

4.3 The kind of Social Capital utilized by young males for survival

4.3.1 Farouk

Farouk is a 30 year old mechanic in one of the garages in Katanga. This is his story.

My father was a mechanic and he encouraged me to join as well. He paid my fees in the garage and also provided me with transport and lunch at times. My brothers are mechanics too but I was encouraged to specialize in bigger vehicles since my dad and brothers are dealing in smaller cars.

Apart from my dad, there is a SACCO (Savings and Credit Cooperative Society) that has been helpful in availing me with some loans. It is Wandegeya Car Mechanism SACCO. This SACCO has been very helpful in helping me have my fees paid at the garage.

We also have rules that guide our work. For instance, late coming is not allowed especially as a student at the garage, by 8:00 am one should have arrived. Theft is also not allowed, if an item goes missing in a customer's vehicle, you pay for it or you are suspended or discontinued and the garage replaces the item. These rules help us retain our customers.

The garage exposes you to different people who can promote your career, For instance one might be lucky and get connected to a driver job in government or an NGO through your customer. Working as a driver is more rewarding than working in the garage, for example, you could earn about 800,000/- (eight hundred thousand shillings) per month which one cannot earn while at the garage.

The kind of social capital utilized in this case includes *bonding, bridging* and *linking* social capital.

Picture 1. An over view of Katanga slum with a garage nearby as indicated by the signpost.

Farouk's response on partners

We have other institutions that are helpful to us. For instance, Centenary bank, the transactions of our SACCO go through this bank. Both men and women benefit from the SACCO though men are the majority for they need the SACCOs to further their businesses. For instance the SACCO has enabled me start a business for my wife – that is hair dressing.

Farouk and gendered use of social capital

We have some government partnership through an institution called JUAKALI UNION and this mainly works with garages and handworks in general providing capital and machinery. It is based in Katwe. It has helped us get more capital for the garage business and garage machinery as well. Women benefit too especially those in tailoring work. In fact there is a tailoring school in Katanga that is run by government. It provides school fees, food and sewing machines for the learners. Therefore am quite satisfied with this initiative.

Differences in survival needs depend on whether one is married or whether they have children. Those who are married tend to have more needs and in most cases they are paid more than those who are not married.

The SACCO has also enabled me start a business for my wife – that is hair dressing.

The linking social capital is therefore utilized by young men and it is enhancing the creation of local jobs as seen above thus promoting local economic development. It is also clear that women are lacking in economic information flow unlike men.

4.3.2 George

He is a 32 year old young man dealing in mobile money and soft drinks in a shop within Katanga. He is married.

I started my business five years ago through my savings, and for the last 4 years, I have benefited from the support of BUMU youth club especially in skills training. We have rules as members of the youth club. For instance we have a constitution and every week, one has to save a minimum of 2000/- (two thousand shillings) and this benefits our businesses. In addition, as members of the youth club we help each other during difficult times like when one has lost a loved one.

The kind of social capital utilized in this case is *linking* social capital.

George's response on partners

Unfortunately I have not benefited from any government initiative but I hear that some get loans. I also think that we have not benefited from government because the leaders do not bring the resources to us at the grass root level.

I would very much want government to provide us with computers, carpentry equipment, sewing machines so as to benefit from the skills that young people have gained especially through the youth clubs and loans too.

George and gendered use of social capital

From my perspective women are more in clubs for they have time for meetings unlike men. In my case I create the time since am self-employed and I have an assistant I can leave behind while am away.

We also have other institutions like Hope for Katanga a local NGO that provides loans and scholarships for boys and girls. I'm also a member of 5 other SACCOs some are located in my

home village. I have benefited from these networks. For instance at BUMU youth club I have acquired entrepreneurship and computer skills, they also teach us how to make charcoal among other skills. We both benefit equally as men and women in this area. However women have extra survival needs like sanitary towels, saloon and makeup needs, men do not need these extras.

4.3.3 Haruna

He is a 22 year old young man who is married. Haruna makes and sells Chapatti and Rolexes in Katanga.

The chapatti business was started after getting a loan from my friends who make up our small SACCO of 20 people. Members of this SACCO are both men and women. We mandatorily contribute a daily deposit of 3000/-(three thousand shillings per day) into the SACCO treasury. This is given to one member of the group each day who is allowed to spend it on his or her own needs. This practice has been on for the last 5 months. When one fails to make that daily contribution, he or she is fined 1000/- (one thousand shillings) more the following day. These principles help us collect some capital for our businesses, pay rent, take care of our families and save as well.

The kind of social capital utilized in this case is *bridging* since it is based on colleagues and friends.

Haruna's response on partners

We do not have any external support much as we need persons that can guide us on how to expand our businesses and also have our small association registered so that we can access relatively bigger loans.

Haruna and gendered use of social capital

We help each other the same way in our businesses no matter whether one is male or female. For instance, if am missing an onion or cabbage for my customer, I can ask my neighbor to give me and am able to serve the customer.

We also have a SACCO here in Katanga but members cannot withdraw money till the 20th of December. Some of us have urgent needs that cannot wait till the end of the year. Therefore such a SACCO can only serve those who can wait till the end of the year. That is why we started our own where we are more certain of regular contribution from our members and no collateral security is

required. We rely on trust and one can only join us when we have studied your ways for some time and your business should be within Katanga.

4.3.4 Innocent

Innocent is a 34 year old young man riding a motorcycle or boda boda to earn a living.

I started this boda boda business after getting a motorcycle loan at 4.5 million Uganda shillings from a rich man. Every week, I have to pay 70,000/- shillings till I finish the entire amount. I have so far ridden it for 10 months. If after 2 weeks, one fails to service the loan, the motor cycle is taken away. If eventually you are able to raise money for those two weeks you are fined 100,000/- These rules are so tough that one hardly gets enough to survive. I do not even have a social life, I'm always working. So far no institution or persons have supported me along the way.

Bridging social capital is evident in the above narration.

Innocent's response on partners

Today we have "safe boda" company that provides us with medical insurance and they pay us on a daily basis whenever we put on their uniform and use their application. Government has neglected us because they think all of us are thugs. Government has failed to distinguish thugs from those who are not thugs trying to make a decent living. I would very much appreciate if government or NGOs can identify and sieve out the evil doers from our business.

Innocent and gendered use of social capital

The boda boda business is mainly for men, and here in Katanga, we have no woman in this business and in several other places as well. In general therefore this business is for men only. Again it is a "do it alone business," if one is sick, they keep their motorcycles till they are well enough to ride again.

As a man, I have to take care of the family unlike women who do not have that burden, so this is where our survival needs differ. The one benefit I can highlight from this business is the fact that it has helped me not to steal otherwise it is a very oppressive kind of business. We are often arrested, mistreated, we have no lawyers and the evil doers are left unpunished.

4.3.5 John

John is 18 years old. He earns a living through washing cars within Katanga. He is a single young man.

I started this job on a part time basis while still in school. It was easy to get some equipment from home like a jerry can, soap and rugs to use in this business. Now I am in my Senior four vacation and I can work fulltime. My fellow workers have always guided me on how to make my work better and now I'm very good at car washing. I have been in this business for two years now.

We have principles that help us run this business smoothly. For instance you are not allowed to steal fuel from the car assigned to you or drive it out of the washing bay. You also have to clean your place of work. Therefore with a clean safe environment, we are able to retain our customers and even attract more. In my social life, my colleagues do correct me in case I misbehave and also lend me money when am in need.

Therefore, from the above it is clear that *bonding and bridging* forms of social capital are being utilized by this young man.

John's response on partners

Government has supported us in our work. For instance in 2016, each registered washing bay around Wandegeya was given a car washing machine and this smoothed our work. Additionally, our SACCO received some money from the government. Some female members of the SACCO were able to use some of that money as capital to start food cooking business. However we have not received any support from civil society.

John and gendered use of social capital

The support given to either a man or woman in this place is the same much as this job is also mainly for men. We just have a few women keeping books of accounts for this business. For instance we have an informal self-help group here, with only 3 women and 13 men. We contribute 10,000/- Ten thousand Uganda Shillings every after 5 days and give it to one of our members. And after another 5 days we give to another person.

The survival needs of men and women differ to some extent. As a man I have to work hard to have some money on me to avoid stealing while a woman can be given money by a boyfriend, husband or

even parents. In addition, there are certain things I cannot ask from my parents much as I'm still in school. For instance, we boys have girlfriends, I cannot ask my parents for money to give to my girlfriend, and therefore I have to work so as to meet this need. With this job, am able to buy myself clothes, a telephone and also have pocket money for school. I'm also happy to be a part of a feminine network as long as it can meet my needs.

Picture 2 - One of the food vendors in Katanga Slum – she takes care of her 3 children through this business. She is one of the members in the men's SACCO

4.3.6 Kefa

Kefa is a 31 year old single man dealing in scrap business. This is his story.

I started dealing in scrap when I was 9 years old. This is a business which does not require any capital as long as you have some energy to collect scrap and the boldness to do it for at times some people think that we are mad. So children, women and men are all involved – they bring their scrap here, we sort it out, weigh it, and pay them. Over 50 people in Katanga and around are in this kind of work in order to get a meal for the day. Everyone is free to start, all one needs is a sac for collecting scrap. We deal a lot in plastics that we sell in bulk to various companies dealing in plastics like Muhozi plastics, Parambot which is along gayaza road among others.

We do have rules. For instance no water or liquids allowed in these used containers or heavy objects like stones. This helps us get the right weights for payment purposes.

Through this business, I have been able to make friends and one of them is teaching me how to repair mobile phones and I do sing with other friends too. Therefore I might take on a music career and soon leave this business for we earn very little.

However we also have challenges in this work. At times children are beaten, being mistaken for thieves and right now one of the kids is inside the shelter, he was badly beaten and we are nursing wounds.

From the above narration, it is clear that *bridging* social capital is being utilized to survive in Katanga.

Kefa's response on partners

We have never experienced any government or civil society intervention probably because they think we are mad. We would very much want to get a hand-out from them but we do not know how to reach out to them.

Picture 3 - One of the scrap centers in Katanga. Plastics are some of the elements under scrap

Kefa and gendered use of social capital

We do assist each other no matter whether one is male or female. For instance, we can put our little money together especially over the weekend and we buy meat, cook and eat in this very place. At times one of our colleagues can offer maize flour and others cook. We eat together as a family and it does not matter whether one contributed or not. Some of us also sleep here, especially the men or boys in case they have nowhere to sleep. This place is home to the homeless, some sleep in the available shelter while others sleep in boxes. However we do not allow women to sleep here.

Picture 4 - At the extreme right is the shelter where some sleep at night

Our survival needs are different. That is, men's clothes and shoes are more expensive than women's clothes. My trousers start from 10,000/- yet you can find a woman's dress at 3,000/-, a blouse at 2000/- and shoes at 5000/-.

We also have challenges in this work, at times children are beaten being mistaken for thieves and right now one of the kids is inside the shelter, he was badly beaten and we are nursing wounds.

From the above, among the men's needs, clothing is more expensive as compared to women's clothing. Clothing is a basic need for survival so this is a big challenge especially to the poor population within Katanga.

The people in scrap business seem to have very strong ties which become more of bonding social capital for they work and live as family, and strive to meet their basic needs for their survival.

4.4 Interpretation of results

4.4.1 Forms of social capital utilized by young men

Therefore from the above narrations, it is clear that men utilize all the three forms of social capital. That is *bonding*, *bridging* and *linking* social capital like the case of Farouk who works in the garage, John the car washer and George, the mobile money dealer. On the other hand, we see

women relying more on bonding and bridging social capital for their survival. None of the women interviewed utilized linking social capital.

The above narratives also indicate that actually men are more active in *linking* social networks or partnerships for their businesses thus promoting local economic development to some extent. For instance, George is in more than 5 SACCOS and all the men interviewed at least belonged to one SACCO.

4.4.2 Partners involved

From the above we see local partnerships at work in this case through the youth clubs and SACCOS. For instance in the case of George the mobile money dealer and Farouk the mechanic. Government's intervention is felt more in the garages and car washing businesses within Katanga where a number of young men work. This therefore shows that linking social capital is being utilized in this case. However, government's contribution is still unfelt among the businesses of some young men especially the boda boda business.

4.4.3 Gendered use of social capital

Some economic activities are gender specific. The boda boda business is mainly for men and this could be because of social upbringing of women where they are expected to do domestic work and not 'male tasks' like riding a motorcycle. It seems to be a tough kind of business too in terms of risks involved like accidents, costs involved in acquiring one and maintaining it yet women are very much limited in economic resources. For instance, a woman feels very insecure taking on a loan of 4.5 million shillings. The car washing and garage businesses are dominated by men as well.

Some of the self-help groups are informal while others are formal. A number of young people in Katanga are involved in various economic activities. They believe in pooling resources together for their survival. Women also seem to have the advantage of being taken care of by parents or boyfriends/husbands to some extent for their survival as in the case of John and Innocent. Men also have more job alternatives to choose from as compared to women and actually men are more involved in income generating activities or LED activities as compared to women. For instance the 5 young men are attached to self-help group while only one woman is in a self-help group in this study.

The scrap business takes care of persons in Katanga without capital. This business enables them earn a meal. It is the most gender inclusive economic activity employing a number of people at the same time as compared to other economic activities in Katanga. For instance, one scrap collection point can employ over 50 persons, including, men, women and children. It is also important to note that this business has rules too. It is also important to note that the scrap dealers are operating in a non-conducive environment but the strong ties or social capital they have keep them going. For instance they cook together, share meals and take care of the sick too.

Young men are more in financial networks trusting colleagues unlike women (Molyneux, 2002). The trust element is revealed as key in social capital building as highlighted by (Hassan & Birungi, 2011; Švihlová & Kubišová, 2014). For instance members in George and Haruna's SACCO base on trust to contribute soft loans among their members.

Men tend to follow rules or principles in their businesses while the young women tend to be relaxed about rules in their businesses. For instance Haruna, Farouk and John have business principles or rules and they follow them strictly unlike Dorah and Carol. This could explain why the young men tend to be more successful in business unlike the young women

The above narrations also shows that survival needs depend on gender roles and responsibilities that is, whether one is married or not and also whether one is male or female. That is, naturally women have particular needs that are different from men's needs. The young women have feminine needs like sanitary towels, makeup unlike men. On the other hand, the married men in the garages are paid much more than the single young men as highlighted by Farouk.

4.4 Discussion of Findings from a Local Economic Development Perspective

Local Economic Development (LED) is all about using the available local resources to create employment opportunities and improve the quality of life of a particular community (Evans & Syrett, 2007). LED therefore involves providing income opportunities through the creation of jobs (International Labour Office, 2010) and this falls under Enterprise development, a LED pillar which caters for both formal and informal employment. This study was able to examine how people living in the slum of Katanga participated in job creation, mostly in the informal sector as they utilize different forms of social capital which were at their disposal. Social capital through family, friends and other persons as depicted in the above findings is key in facilitating the creation of jobs and enabling the LED process within the area.

Some of the major resources like capital, skills, are accessed through social networks of friends or relatives thus embracing the notion of the *bridging* and *bonding* forms of social capital respectively, in this case. Who one knows facilitates their access to local resources (Triglia, 2001), which enables slum dwellers or the young women and men of Katanga in particular to create income generating activities/ employment opportunities for their survival. It is important to note that most young women have no collateral security so the social networks or social capital become very key in accessing local resources for their survival. For example Anita was able to get a loan from a friend in money lending business without collateral security.

4.5 Conclusion

In conclusion, Katanga slum is a busy place where everyone endeavors to survive. Men tend to have the advantage of all forms of social capital and therefore have the potential to benefit more from local development partnerships unlike most young women who seem to have no information about available partnerships that they can maximize and improve their wellbeing.

CHAPTER FIVE

5.0 Introduction

The study investigated the forms of social capital being utilized in Katanga by young women and men. The partners involved or *linking* social capital and the gendered use of social capital was investigated as well. The methods of inquiry were qualitative in nature and these included unstructured interviews, non-participatory observation and document analysis.

5.1 Summary on Findings

Findings suggest that all the three forms of social capital exist in Katanga among young women and men. The *bonding* and *bridging* forms of social capital are more prevalent and facilitate their livelihood while the *linking* social capital is more among young men. With linking social capital among young men there is still more potential for local economic development since linking social capital is key to local development (Woolcock & Narayan, 2000).

Since linking social capital is very much absent among young women therefore there is need to bridge the information gap that exists among young women so that they too can benefit from linking social capital initiatives. The limiting factors to credit facilities or linking social capital initiatives should be removed by government and local NGOs so that women can also get access to credit facilities without first availing collateral security. In this case micro finance institutions and banks specifically set up for the poor like the Grameen bank model which was founded in Bangladesh (Grameen Bank, 2019). Such a bank should be availed to young women in slums so as to enable them engage in local economic activities more effectively.

This study also shows that as far as gendered social capital is concerned, men are more in beneficial networks like SACCOs while women are more in non-monetary activities. This is in agreement with (Molyneux, 2002; Norris & Inglehart, 2003). There is therefore need to address the limiting factors that prevent young women from participating fully in linking social capital initiatives.

5.2 Recommendations

Women should be encouraged to participate in economic networks especially at an early age so that they embrace economic ventures. The notion of having African young women in the kitchen should be left behind and instead encourage young women take up various roles in society including local economic activities.

Time that women invest in various activities should be rewarded and not taken for granted in form of some allowances. For instance, stay at home mothers or those involved in voluntary work can be given a living allowances too so that they can survive or meet some of their basic needs.

Improving the flow of economic information in slums especially among young women will go a long way in empowering them and enable them run and expand their businesses thus bringing about local economic development. This can be through establishing information hubs within slum areas where they can access information on jobs, skilling opportunities, et cetera.

More research on the building and utilization of social capital in slums should be done for not much has been done on this subject in Uganda. More qualitative and quantitative studies can be carried out so as to address missing gaps in social capital utilization and local economic development.

Local governments, Non-governmental organizations should deliberately plan to grow social capital especially in slum areas. This can be through joint activities like games, sports and drama. For instance when local government staff interact with slum dwellers, they are able to understand their needs better. This also creates safer cities which encourages more innovation, creation of more local economic activities thus creating more jobs and promoting local economic development.

5.3 Conclusion

Therefore in conclusion, with more development of *linking* social capital in slums, more young women and men are able to participate in income generating activities, earn and improve their wellbeing. When more economic activities are generated in slums, in partnership with government and other linking capital partners, more investments will be made thus promoting local economic development in slums.

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